

HISTORY AND EVOLUTION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REFLECTIVE TEACHING TECHNOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17813830>

Abstract. *The article examines the history and development of reflective teaching technology, aiming to demonstrate its pedagogical value and its role in fostering students' critical thinking. The article explores the origins and evolution of the concept of reflection in philosophical and pedagogical discourse, identifies the functions and features of reflective methods, and determines the pedagogical conditions necessary for developing learners' ability to independently analyze and evaluate their own actions. The findings indicate that reflection is a key mechanism for understanding learning activities, enhancing creative and critical thinking, increasing learners' independence, and developing their skills of self-control and self-assessment. The practical use of reflective technologies improves the effectiveness of the educational process, makes learning more conscious and meaningful, and strengthens pedagogical communication. The article concludes that reflection is a continuous process of analysis and self-development, and its systematic application is an essential element of modern education focused on personal growth and active student involvement.*

Keywords: *reflection; reflective teaching technology; critical thinking; pedagogical process; self-analysis; self-assessment; personal development; educational activity; pedagogical conditions; creative thinking.*

ANNOTATSIYA . *Maqolada reflektiv o'qitish texnologiyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanish tarixi ko'rib chiqilib, uning pedagogik ahamiyati hamda o'quvchilarda tanqidiy tafakkurni shakllantirishdagi o'rni yoritiladi. Maqolada "refleksiya" tushunchasining falsafiy va pedagogik manbalardagi kelib chiqishi va rivoji tahlil qilinadi, reflektiv metodlarning vazifalari va qo'llash xususiyatlari aniqlanadi, shuningdek, o'quvchilarda o'z faoliyatini mustaqil tahlil qilish va baholash qobiliyatini rivojlantiruvchi pedagogik sharoitlar belgilab beriladi. Olingan natijalar refleksiya o'quv faoliyatini anglashning asosiy mexanizmi ekanini, ijodiy va tanqidiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishini, mustaqillikni oshirishini va o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishini ko'rsatadi. Reflektiv texnologiyalardan amaliy foydalanish ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi, o'quv jarayonini ongli va mazmunli qiladi, pedagogik muloqotni yaxshilaydi. Tadqiqot xulosalariga ko'ra, refleksiya uzluksiz tahlil va o'zini rivojlantirish jarayoni bo'lib, uning tizimli qo'llanilishi shaxsiy rivojlanishga va o'quvchilarning faol ishtirokiga yo'naltirilgan zamonaviy ta'limning muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *refleksiya; reflektiv o'qitish texnologiyasi; tanqidiy tafakkur; pedagogik jarayon; o'z-o'zini tahlil qilish; o'zini baholash; shaxsiy rivojlanish; ta'lim faoliyati; pedagogik shart-sharoitlar; ijodiy tafakkur.*

АННОТАЦИЯ. *В статье рассматривается история становления и развития рефлексивной технологии обучения, цель которой состоит в раскрытии её педагогической значимости и роли в формировании критического мышления обучающихся. В статье анализируются происхождение и эволюция понятия «рефлексия»*

в философской и педагогической традиции, выявляются функции и особенности применения рефлексивных методов, а также определяются педагогические условия, способствующие развитию у студентов способности к самостоятельному анализу и оценке собственной деятельности. Полученные результаты показывают, что рефлексия является важнейшим механизмом осмысления учебной деятельности, способствует развитию творческого и критического мышления, повышает уровень самостоятельности и формирует навыки самоконтроля и самооценки. Практическое применение рефлексивных технологий позволяет повысить эффективность образовательного процесса, сделать обучение более осознанным и результативным, а также улучшить педагогическую коммуникацию. В заключение подчёркивается, что рефлексия представляет собой непрерывный процесс анализа и саморазвития, а её системное использование является важным компонентом современного образования, ориентированного на личностный рост и активное участие обучающихся.

Ключевые слова: рефлексия; рефлексивная технология обучения; критическое мышление; педагогический процесс; самоанализ; самооценка; развитие личности; образовательная деятельность; педагогические условия; творческое мышление.

INTRODUCTION. The emergence of all educational systems in the world has always been predetermined and conditioned by the socio-economic demands of society. The overarching goal of these systems is to provide society with an educated individual who is capable of independent critical thinking, generating new ideas, thinking creatively; independently acquiring and applying knowledge in practice; skillfully working with information - searching for it, analyzing, systematizing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and making constructive proposals; being communicative and sociable within various social groups, able to work collaboratively in different fields and situations, preventing or skillfully resolving conflict situations; independently working on the development of one's moral values, intellect, and cultural level. It is precisely this goal that is addressed through the use of reflective learning technology in the educational process within the system of lifelong learning, which is confirmed by the analysis of scholarly and methodological literature on this issue.

MAIN PART. The term *reflection* originates from the Latin word *reflexio*, meaning "turning back," that is, the ability of a person to comprehend their own experience in order to reach new understanding, evaluate, and justify their own beliefs and value orientations.

In a narrow sense, reflection is the comprehension of one's own activity, a turning back "inside" the activity with the aim of improving it; a research-oriented position within any activity. In a broad sense, reflection is stepping outside any immediate, "automatically" occurring process or state. [4]

Reflection is understood as a mental property of consciousness or the ability to objectively evaluate one's life situation. Considering the history of the concept, it should be noted that an idea similar to reflection appeared in ancient philosophy.

The analysis of the literature shows that *reflection* was first formulated by Socrates and Platon, who believed that it was necessary for understanding oneself and one's place in the world.

However, the essential point is that reflection was originally understood not as a specific concept, but as a way of justifying moral, aesthetic and other values.

The term *reflection* was first used in scientific discourse by the English educator and philosopher John Locke in the 17th century in his work *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, which he wrote over the course of twenty years. John Locke defines reflection as “... the observation which the mind makes upon its own operations and the manner of them; thereby producing ideas of those operations... a person is a thinking intelligent being that has reason and reflection, and can consider itself as itself...” [3]

In *The Phénomène Humain*, Pierre Teilhard de Chardin defines reflection as follows: “...from the point of view we take, reflection is the acquired ability of consciousness to focus upon itself and to possess itself as an object... the ability not merely to know, but to know oneself; not simply to be aware, but to be aware that one is aware.” [5]

It should also be noted that one of the first to use reflection in literary criticism was V. G. Belinsky, when analyzing M. Y. Lermontov’s novel *A Hero of Our Time*.

G. P. Shchedrovitsky points out that reflection is an important element in the mechanisms of the development of activity, upon which all forms of organization of activity depend, including the meaning of texts and the significance of individual signs and expressions. [7]

L. S. Kozhukhovskaya and I. V. Poznyak in their work *Reflective Techniques, Methods, and Approaches*, dedicated to analyzing and applying various forms of reflection, examine specific methods and techniques that can be used both in pedagogical practice and in personal development, helping individuals understand themselves and adjust their behavior. They identify the following key aspects of reflection:

- **Reflection as a process of self-analysis:** studying one’s thoughts, feelings, and behavior, and evaluating them for a better understanding of oneself and others.
- **Pedagogical application:** analyzing one’s own activity and its results, understanding the developmental prospects of learners.
- **Reflection of content:** discussing and evaluating the material studied at the end of a lesson or another stage to comprehend its content and the effectiveness of one’s own work.
- **Reflective learning:** using the strengths and experience of others to improve one’s own learning and adapt to changing conditions.
- **Cooperative reflection:** evaluating joint activity to achieve a common goal, including the analysis of the situation, tasks, responsibilities, organization of work, and comparison of goals and results. [2]

E. N. Shvets, in her study *The Use of Reflection Technologies in the Pedagogical Process*, describes the concept of reflection, its specific features, and its role in solving professional tasks of supplementary education teachers. She provides examples of practical applications of reflection technologies in group and individual work with students and educators. [6]

According to modern scholars, reflection helps individuals understand why people think and act in certain ways and then find opportunities to improve their emotional state and behavioral patterns.

Drawing on existing definitions, we formulated our own. In our view, reflection is a process of interrelated activity between the teacher and the students aimed at acquiring knowledge, skills, and competencies, during which students independently evaluate and analyze the information received, the results of their learning activity, their own condition, and emotions. Reflective technology performs several important functions. It enables students to consciously plan, regulate, and control their thinking; evaluate not only the truth of their thoughts but also

their logical correctness. Reflection not only improves the results of problem-solving but also enables solving problems that cannot be resolved without its application. It should also be noted that in the pedagogical process reflection contributes to solving such tasks as designing and modeling the activity of participants in the educational process; organizing the most effective forms of interaction in joint learning activities; communication that fosters productive interaction; and retrospection that facilitates critical analysis, generalization, and systematization of accumulated knowledge.

It can be confidently stated that today reflection is a well-established concept widely used in science and teaching practice. Reflection cannot be taught directly, but pedagogical conditions can be created under which reflection is most likely to arise in students' consciousness.

CONCLUSION. All of the above allows us to conclude that reflection is a process of continuous analysis of one's own activity and its results. The use of reflective technology in the classroom makes the learning process more effective and engaging, allowing teachers to analyze students' achievements, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and helping them understand the purpose of learning, which acts as a motivational factor encouraging academic engagement. Reflective technology stimulates students' intellectual and creative activity, enhances their independence and initiative in the learning process, reduces tension, and cultivates self-control and self-assessment.

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